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Analysing the Changing Trends of Literacy in Deoria District: A Case Study

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Abstract

The concept of literacy has undergone significant change over time. A low level of literacy in the district in the past has generally been attributed to factors like caste-based social system, primarily agricultural-based economy, low rate of population mobility, predominantly rural society, unfavourable social values towards literacy prejudice against female education and mobility, extreme poverty and above all rapid growth in population. The 2011 census indicates the most significant aspect in the district is the fact that the absolute number of illiterate in the district has shown a decline and the female literacy has recorded a much larger increase as compared to the male literacy which narrowed the gap between male and female literacy during this period. This paper is an attempt to analyse the wide regional disparity in literacy in context to the literacy at the block level, difference in male and female literacy, urban and rural literacy, scheduled caste and scheduled tribe literacy and the factors affecting the literacy in Deoria district.

Keywords: Literacy Rate, Mortality, Multi-Linguistic Society, Population Growth Rate, Migratory Patterns, Immigrants, Demographic Attributes.

Introduction:

Literacy is an index of socio-cultural and economic advancement of a region. It also reflects the political maturity of a society. Degree of literacy is the basic parameter for measuring educational status. Literacy acts as a tool for eradicating poverty and mental isolation. It helps in cultivating peaceful and friendly inter-relations. Any investment on education therefore brings prosperity and social prestige to an area. Literacy also determines other attributes of population i.e. fertility, mortality, occupational structure etc. Illiteracy, on the other hand, is a great obstacle to the economic and socio-cultural growth of any region. It takes away dignity from man and develops ignorance, poverty and mental isolation. It retards social advancement, economic growth and political maturity in a region. As such it becomes a matter of prime importance for population geographers to study the level and standard of literacy in a region.

The above discussion shows that literacy influences other demographic attributes like fertility, mortality, economic patterns, social consciousness and per capita income in an area. The economic development and political consciousness in Kerala and West Bengal are closely linked with the high literacy rate in those states. Prof. S. Mukherjee, while studying the fertility behaviours of women in Birbhum district of West Bengal found a close relationship between the level of education and fertility rates. According to him the fertility rate decreases with the rise in the level of education in women. For example illiterate women have 5.2 children on an average while in case of 10+ educated women, the number of children per mother drops to only 2.2.

The concept of literacy refers to the minimum level of literacy skill. The definition of literacy varies from country to country. In some countries the length of schooling has been considered as a basis for distinguishing between literates and illiterates. But Triwartha thinks that the length of schooling cannot be the valid basis for the measurement of education level. High ability to read and write one's name in the language of his country cannot be the valid

criteria for defining a literate person. The population commission of the United Nations includes those persons under literates who have ability to both read and write a simple message with understanding in any language. The Indian census has adopted the definition suggested by the population commission of the United Nations. This definition is gradually becoming popular in many countries. But there is a difference between literate and educated persons. In India, attempts have been made to distinguish literates and illiterates. The literates may also be divided into further sub-categories on the basis of the length of schooling. Some countries of the world exclude every age group of below 10 years from their literacy statics because a child can acquire minimum literacy skill only after 5 years of schooling.

Study Area:

Deoria district is situated in the north eastern part of Uttar Pradesh. Formerly it was a tehsil of Gorakhpur district but got separated in 1946 as the independent district. The study area extends from 26° 6' N and 26° 48' N latitudes to 83° 23' E and 84° 16' E longitudes. It has a total area of 2527.2 sq. km. In the north, the study area is bounded by the District Kushinagar while the districts of Ballia and Azamgarh of Uttar Pradesh form its Southern boundary. In the east, it is delineated by the Uttar Pradesh-Bihar border across which lie the West Champaran, Gopalganj and Siwan districts of Bihar. Gorakhpur district, from which the study area has been separated, forms its Western boundary. The river Ghagara flows along the southern boundary of the district.

According to the 2011 census Deoria district has a population of 3,100,946, roughly equal to the nation of Mongolia or the US state of Iowa. This gives it a ranking of 114th in India (out of a total of 640). The district has a population density of 1,220 inhabitants per sq.km. Its population growth rate over the decade 2001-2011 was 14.23%. Deoria has a sex ratio of 1013 females for every 1000 males, and a literacy rate of 71.13%.

The Study Area

Methodology:

This paper is based on the primary survey work of 170 families and their experiences from the five villages (Kanhauli, Tendua, Siswa, Sonbarsa, and Sahiya) of Deoria District, which is usually collected by the questionnaire and through the individual interviews. The secondary data is collected from the Census Handbook of Deoria district and reviewed published sources. The approach to analyse the population-literacy data is both quantitative and qualitative. The methodologies used to analyse the data are observational descriptive and observational relational, while in absence of data at some places a hypothetical method is also applied to get the desired result.

Objective:

1. Analysing the factors such as economy, degree of urbanisation, means of transport & communication, language, etc affecting the literacy in Deoria district.
2. Discussing the influence of literacy on the demographic attributes like fertility, mortality, economic patterns, social consciousness, etc.
3. Analysing the changing trends of literacy in Deoria district.
4. Finding the impact of literacy on the population growth in the district.

The Trends of Literacy in Deoria District:

Deoria district took its shape as an independent district in 1946 so no separate census was conducted before 1951. The first regular and systematic census was conducted in 1961. Hence the present discussion on the trends of literacy in Deoria district is based on the census reports of 1951 and onwards. The higher literacy rate is found in the upper caste population even today. But literacy is gradually becoming popular among Sudras or Scheduled caste population. Table A clearly depicts the trends of literacy in Deoria district since 1951. In 1951, 9.5% of the total population of the district were literate. The literacy rate increased to 13.53% in 1961, 19.59% in 1971, 24.86% in 1981, 33.36% in 1991 and 48.93% in 2001 but the greatest growth of the literacy rate was seen in 2011 when it increased to 71.1%.

Trends of Literacy Rate in Deoria District in Percentage

Years	Total Literacy	Male Literacy	Female Literacy	Population Growth
1951-61	13.53%	23.16%	3.90%	12.40%
1961-71	19.59%	32.28%	6.81%	18.30%
1971-81	24.86%	40.18%	10.07%	24.20%
1981-91	42.42%	61.48%	23.58%	24.90%
1991-01	59.84%	76.31%	43.56%	23.10%
2001-11	71.10%	83.30%	59.40%	14.20%

In all the census years right from the 1951 to 2011 male literacy rate dominated over female literacy rates. Both male and female literacy rate shows upward trends since 1951. But female literacy lags behind male literacy in all the census years. According to the 2011 census male literacy rate in Deoria district was 83.3% whereas female literacy rate in Deoria district was 59.4%. Table A clearly shows that female literacy never exceeded 45% till 2001 but there was a drastic change during 2001-11 when it rose to 59.4%. The female literacy has remained low in all the census year since 1951 but the rate of progress in female literacy is higher than male literacy since 1991, when during this period male literacy rate has increased from 61.48% in 1991 to 83.3% in 2011 whereas the female literacy rate has recorded an increase from 23.58% in 1991 to 59.4% in 2011 in the same period. The status of the female in the society is the main constraint in the way of female literacy.

In the district 77.1% of the population is literate as against 67.7% in the state of Uttar Pradesh. In the district 83.3% of the male population is literate as compared to 77.3% in the state. However, among females the literacy in the district is 59.4% as compared to 52.7% at the state level. In the district literacy rate is 80.0% in urban areas as against 70.1% in rural areas. The gap in male/female literacy rate is 26.4% points in rural areas as compared to 19.7% in urban areas. The literacy rate among C.D. blocks vary between 67.49% in Rudrapur to 73.21% in Bhagalpur. Similarly, the literacy rate among towns varies from 68.66% in Majhauri Raj NP to 86.8% in Deoria NPP.

In Deoria district from 1961 to 1991 the literacy rate was proportional to the population growth rate, when the literacy rate was 13.53% in 1961, 19.59% in 1971, 24.86% in 1981 and 42.42% in 1991 during this period the population growth rate was 12.4% in 1991 during this period the population growth rate was 12.4% in 1961, 18.3% in 1971, 24.2% in 1981 and 24.9% in 1991. But in the last two decades when literacy rate became much higher 59.84% in 2001 which increased to 71.1% in 2011, the population growth rate was inversely proportional i.e. 23.1% in 2001 and 14.2% in 2011.

Spatial Variation in Literacy:

Literacy in Deoria district shows great spatial variation. It varies from one block to the other. It is evident from the table that the percentage of literacy rate in the district in the year 2011 varies between 67.97% and 76.61%. The highest percentage is found in Deoria Sadar as it is shown in the table B because it is the district headquarter with a large urban centre, followed by Salempur, Bhagalpur, Lar, Bhatni and Bhatpar Rani have better educational facilities with number of primary and secondary schools due to the urban centres and dense network of transport and communication facilities. All these blocks have a high percentage of upper caste population compared to the backward caste and scheduled caste. Bhagalpur block has high literacy rate due to the contribution of minority educational institutes while Desai Deoria block being close to district headquarter gets every facility very easily. The lowest literacy rate is found in Baitalpur. The other blocks with low literacy rate less than 70% are Rudrapur, Tarkulwa, Pathar Dewa, Rampur Karkhana, Barhaj, Gauri Bazar, Bankata and Bhaluani.

Male and Female Literacy:

Marked difference between male and female literacy can be observed in Deoria district. Table B clearly shows the variation of male literacy rate in different blocks of the district in 2011. The male literacy varies between 80.19% and 85.93%. The highest male literacy rate has been recorded in Deoria Sadar and lowest in Barhaj. Three blocks i.e. Deoria, Bhatni and Salempur have the highest male literacy rate.

The start of the new millennium has seen the new trends also in the female literacy evident from table B as the average female literacy rate in Deoria district is 59.4% in 2011. But there is great spatial variation in its distribution. Female literacy rate in the study area varies between 55.25% and 67.01%. The maximum literacy rate is registered in Deoria Sadar and the minimum in Baitalpur. Five blocks i.e. Deoria, Salempur, Rudrapur, Bhagalpur and Lar have more than 60% literacy rate, the highest in the district. Deoria is the district headquarter, Christian missionaries in Bhagalpur and urban centres in Lar and Salempur are responsible for high female literacy rate in these blocks. Four blocks Desai Deoria, Bhatni, Bhatpar Rani and Barhaj are urban centres. In these urban centres better education facilities for females are available. The lowest category of female literacy rate covers five blocks of the district. These are Baitalpur, Tarkulwa, Bankatta, Gauri Bazar and Patthardewa. These blocks have a rural background.

Urban and Rural Literacy:

Table C shows the spatial variations of literacy rate in both urban and rural population in Deoria district in 2011. It is evident from the table that literacy rate varies greatly between the urban and rural population, 80.04% of urban population in Deoria district is literate while in rural areas the literacy rate has been recorded only 70.09%. In this way, rural literacy is 10% less than urban literacy. It is more interesting to note that the rural-urban differential in literacy is sharper in case of females than males. The female literacy rate in the urban areas is 72.82% while in the rural areas 57.91% of the female population is literate. The male literacy in urban and rural areas in the district is 86.77% and 82.84% respectively. The rural-urban literacy differential in the district is due to the difference in economy, social life and migratory patterns of the two areas. The type of economy found in urban areas requires basic skill of education as a prerequisite. Urban literacy in the district varies between 68.66% in Majhauri Raj NP and 86.8% in Deoria NPP. Above table reveals that literacy rate is high in the urban areas of the district (80.04%). The literacy rate is quite high (above 85.0%) in Deoria (NPP). In case of male literacy it is above 90% in Deoria (NPP), Salempur (NP). Female literacy rate is not far behind in Deoria (NPP) and Salempur (NP) which is above 75%. However, literacy rate among females is very low (57.72%) in Majhauri Raj (NP), thus the gap in male-female literacy rate is highest (21.65% points).

Rural literacy in the district varies between 67.49% and 73.21%. The maximum rural literacy rate is found in Bhagalpur and minimum in the Rudrapur block. Low rural literacy rate is found in purely rural blocks except Bhagalpur (73.21%) and Bhaluani (69.91%). High rural literacy rates are expected in those blocks, which have both rural and urban character. But it is not true with Deoria district. There is a perfect positive correlation between total literacy and rural literacy.

Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe Literacy:

Scheduled caste and scheduled tribe constitute the lower status of the society. Like other parts of India, as well as Uttar Pradesh, they are a socially, economically and educationally backward segment of population in Deoria district. As such, the literacy rate among the scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population lags behind the general literacy rate of the district. The general literacy rate of the Deoria district has been registered as 71.1% in 2011 while the literacy rate among scheduled castes is 63.23%. Thus it is evident that the literacy rate in scheduled caste is lower than the general literacy rate in the district. However the literacy rate among the scheduled tribe is 67.35% higher than the scheduled caste literacy. One of the interesting features to be noted in literacy among scheduled caste and scheduled tribes is that the number of female literates is low i.e. 50.19% and 54.63% respectively. The most interesting fact is the male literacy rate in scheduled caste and scheduled tribe is 93.96% and 80.66% respectively which is much higher than the total male literacy rate in Deoria district.

Maximum scheduled caste literacy is found in Desai Deoria (66.72%) and the minimum in Barha (59.8%). Bhatpar Rani, Bhagalpur, Salempur, Bhatni, Bankata, Tarkulwa, Deoria are the other blocks having more than 64% literacy rate while Lar, Gauri Bazar, Bhaluani, Baitalpur, Pathar Dewa, Rampur Karkhana and Rudrapur are the other blocks which have less than 64% literacy rate. Most of the scheduled caste population is engaged in agriculture, as agricultural labourers.

Results and Findings:

1. Type of Economy: The economy of an area is well reflected in the literacy rate. The type of economy is considered to be the most dominant determinant of literacy patterns in Deoria district. According to Golden, even the art of writing has been influenced by economic

diversification. The difference in the literacy rate between the agricultural and urban places in the district is related to the difference in the economic conditions.

2. The Willingness and Ability of People to Learn: The willingness and ability of people to learn seems to be the most dominant influencing literacy level in Deoria. "Early malnutrition and disease can be performed by arithmetic operations and thinking logically and clearly in school". The ability to learn depends upon the environment of the family including income level, education of parents, housing conditions, number of children in the household etc.

3. Degree of Urbanisation: Next important determinant of literacy rate is the degree of urbanisation. Urban areas have a relatively higher literacy rate than the surrounding rural areas. The employment opportunities available in the urban areas require literacy and education as a prerequisite.

4. Degree of Development of Means of Transport and Communication: The recent advancement and improvement in the means of transport and communication have improved and added a new dimension in the expansion of literacy and education. The developed means of transport brings remote rural areas into close contact with advanced urban and industrial areas and breaks rural isolation. This contact improves the mental faculty of the rural population and enhances literacy rate in rural areas.

5. The Language: Language is another factor determining literacy. In a multilingual society, the medium of instruction in the mother tongue of the local people can improve literacy rate. Example may again be cited from the Muslim communities, who are aversion towards the other medium of instruction than their mother tongue Urdu.

6. The Status of Women in the Society: The status of women in the society is another important factor determining literacy rate in an area. Women constitute about 50% of the total population. Hence any discrimination between men and women in the matter of their status can adversely affect literacy rate. In that society where women are not provided equal rights or status, the literacy rate is lower. The low female literacy rate ultimately adversely affects the general literacy rate.

7. The Availability of Education Facilities: The availability of education facilities also play a vital role in literacy transition in an area. Positive correlation is found between availability of educational facilities and literacy rate.

8. Public Policies Formulated by Government: Public policies formulated by government, such as free and compulsory education, campaign against illiteracy, adult education programme, etc. plays a positive role in the propagation of literacy among people.

9. Conventional Education: Most of the educational institutions in the district provide conventional education which doesn't prepare the students to get a job, the job oriented education is available only in highly developed urban places.

10. The Success of Government Literacy Programs: In 1951 the total literacy rate in the district was 9.5% which increased to 71.1% in 2011; this also shows the success of the National Adult Education Program (NAEP), Rural Functional Literacy Program (RFLP), National Literacy Mission (NLM), etc. carried by the NGOs backed by State and Central Government.

11. Higher Literacy Rate than State: The literacy rate in the district 77.1% is much higher as against 67.7% in the state of Uttar Pradesh in 2011 i.e. due to the high upper caste population in the district as there is more awareness among these castes.

12. Spatial Variation in Literacy at the Block Level: There is a spatial variation in the literacy at the block level, as some blocks have better educational facilities with a number of primary and secondary schools due to larger urban centres and dense network of transport and communication facilities.

13. Low Female Literacy Rate: The female literacy rate is low in the district as in the state in all the census years. It is due to the government's effort that the female literacy rate in 2011 increased to 59.4% but in the scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population it is still very low due to their conservative mindset.

14. The Female Literacy Rate is Inversely Proportional to the Population Growth: The female literacy rate was proportional to the population growth till 1991 but in 2001 when the female literacy rate reached to 43.56% the first time the population growth slightly came down to 23.1% which again came down to 14.2% in 2011 when the female literacy rate was 59.4%.

15. Higher Overall Literacy Rate among the STs than SCs: The literacy rate among the scheduled tribe is higher than the scheduled caste population because the overall population of ST is very less in the district and mostly, they are immigrants, usually settled in the district for the government job so they are more aware to the education.

Conclusion:

The urban areas have the basically non-agricultural economy, the acquisition of minimum literacy skill is prerequisite in the urban areas. In rural areas where agricultural pursuits are predominant no special skill is required. In well-educated families with better income and fewer children, the literacy rate is high. Better facilities of education are available in urban areas in comparison to rural areas. There is a positive correlation between literacy rate and the degree of the development of the means of transport and communication. The improved transport facilities and the children from the rural areas can go to the town easily and communication cultivated awareness among people in the rural societies towards education and the rural people start making use of educational institutions which are located in urban areas.

The literacy rate is relatively higher in Christian communities because they provide equal status to both men and women. In closed Muslim societies equal right is not provided to women. Hence there is low literacy rate among Muslim communities. The prejudice against female education and mobility plays a negative role in the general literacy rate. High literacy rate is found in those areas where the number of persons per educational institution is low. The adult literacy programme adopted by the government of India after independence has played a vital role in eradicating mass illiteracy in Deoria district. The changing government policies due to the pandemic playing an important role in the pattern of education. The higher literacy rate than the state proves the success of the government literacy programs. The spatial variation in literacy at the block level and the low female literacy rate is due to the rigidity in the families in the remote areas very far from the urban areas.

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